

Genetic resources program

Rice germplasm collected from low-lying areas of Orissa

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As a part of the India-wide rice germplasm collection program formulated in 1978, CRRI surveyed and collected rice germplasm from the typical low-lying areas of

Orissa in 1978 kharif.

Although the germplasm in those areas in India is not threatened by immediate extinction (most current improved varieties are not suitable for such conditions), collection in such areas is being emphasized to locate donors for the development of improved varieties for flood-prone and waterlogged areas, which make up about a third of India's

total rice area.

The survey resulted in the collection of 140 typical low-lying varieties. Some varieties such as Rabana, Dhusara, Magura, Champeisali, Cuttack Chandi, and Ratnachudi are common in several blocks. All the varieties collected, including two scented types, were late maturing with coarse, fine, or very fine grain. They are being evaluated under waterlogged conditions in 1979 kharif. More than 15,000 viable accessions are now in the national germplasm collection at CRRI. ■

Grain quality

An X-ray technique to screen sun cracks in rice grains

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Sun cracks develop in mature rice grains exposed to variable humidity and temperature. Overmature crops left in the field or threshed grain left in the open are exposed to low temperature and humidity at night and high temperature and low humidity in daylight hours. The alternate soaking and drying lead to the "sun cracking" of the endosperm. The sun-cracked grains invariably break during hulling and milling. Other grains break independently of sun-cracking because of mechanical damage. When evaluating varieties for head-rice recovery, the broken kernels are separated after milling and expressed as a percentage of rough rice. But there has been no method to determine if sun-cracking or mechanical damage caused the breakage. Therefore head-rice recovery has been considered subjective and inheritance studies on the trait have been inconclusive.

An X-ray technique has been used to measure the degree of damage caused by sun cracks, thus allowing separate determination of breakage due to milling.

Grains with sun crack (white arrow) and mechanical damage (black arrow). Pantnagar, India.

An X-ray inspection unit (Faxitron model 804, 14 kV, current 2mA) was used. Rice samples suspected of high damage were spread on an X-ray plate 25 cm from the source. The samples were exposed for 3 seconds, then the plates

were developed by the usual method. The cracks and damage appeared in the plate clearly (see photo). Damaged grain can also be counted from positive plates. The technique may be useful to breeders in determining genotypic differences and

inheritance of breakage components, and would ultimately help in the development of varieties with high head-rice recovery. Agronomists and technicians may use the method to develop recommendations on date of harvest, cultivation practices, drying method, and processing to ensure high head-rice recovery. ■

Microorganisms associated with spotted and discolored rice grains in Bangladesh

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In Bangladesh, discoloration of rice grain (i.e. grain spotting) seems to have increased with the cultivation of high yielding varieties and the use of high nitrogen rates. Some varietal and seasonal differences in grain spotting seem to occur. The actual causes of spotting have not been confirmed. Although microorganisms have been found associated with it, pathogens of seedborne diseases could be involved. An attempt was made to isolate and identify the organisms associated with spotted and discolored rice grains. Grains from different varieties were collected at maturity by harvesting intact panicles during 1978 boro, aus, and T. aman at the BRRI farm. The healthy and spotted or discolored grains from each panicle were separated and the percentages of spotted grains per variety were calculated. About 100 spotted grains of each variety were then dehulled.

Unhulled and dehulled grains were then surface-sterilized in 0.5% NaClO for 5 minutes and 3 minutes, respectively, and plated at 10 grains/plate on potato dextrose agar (PDA) and Blotter. The plates were incubated for 10 to 14 days at about 28°C. Microorganisms in the grains grew in about 3 days of incubation. Some were transferred to fresh PDA plates for purification, sporulation, and identification; others were examined directly under the microscope and identified. The total numbers of each type of organism from grains of each variety were then recorded. Twenty microorganisms — 17 fungi, 2 bacteria, and

Microorganisms isolated from spotted and discolored rice grains and the frequency of occurrence in different varieties and seasons in Bangladesh.

Organisms isolated	Occurrence (%) ^a									
	Boro		Aus				T. aman			
	Hbj BII	IR8	Chan- dina	BR3	BR6	BR8	IR20	BR3	BR6	BR8
<i>Acrocyndrium oryzae</i>	—	—	—	3	2	1	—	4	—	5
<i>Aspergillus</i> spp.	6	14	2	2	2	4	—	—	1	—
<i>Cephalosporium</i> sp.	—	—	13	13	25	25	—	—	16	10
<i>Chaetomium</i> sp.	—	—	2	4	7	3	—	—	—	1
<i>Curvularia lunata</i>	5	3	7	10	16	4	18	9	25	12
<i>Drechslera oryzae</i>	7	6	6	14	10	13	8	15	28	22
<i>Eurotium</i> sp.	1	1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
<i>Fusarium</i> spp.	1	1	7	8	8	13	11	4	4	10
<i>Nigrospora oryzae</i>	—	—	1	—	—	—	11	—	—	—
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	—	—	5	2	2	5	—	—	—	—
<i>Phoma</i> sp.	—	—	2	—	8	8	—	—	—	—
<i>Pyrenochaeta</i> sp.	—	—	—	2	11	5	—	—	—	—
<i>Trichoconis padwickii</i>	6	5	1	16	22	9	5	38	62	52
Unidentified sp. I	—	—	2	2	5	—	—	—	1	—
" sp. II	—	—	2	—	2	—	—	—	—	—
" sp. III	—	—	1	—	—	—	5	5	—	—
" sp. IV	—	—	1	2	1	2	—	—	—	1
<i>Actinomycetes</i> sp.	5	9	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
<i>Bacterium</i> (white)	—	—	10	7	10	1	—	—	—	—
<i>Bacterium</i> (yellow)	—	—	14	3	9	41	—	3	4	9
Spotted grains/panicle (%)	6	9	44	55	31	96	54	52	35	61

^aCalculated from total number of colonies appearing among 100 to 200 plated, discolored seeds per variety.

1 actinomycete — were found associated with spotted and discolored grains (see table). The most commonly isolated organisms were *Curvularia lunata*, *Trichoconis padwickii*, *Cephalosporium* sp., *Drechslera oryzae*, *Fusarium* sp., and a yellow bacterium. Those that were isolated from both unhulled and dehulled grains were *Acrocyndrium oryzae*, *D. oryzae*, *T. padwickii*, *Fusarium* sp., *Aspergillus* sp., *Cephalosporium* sp., *C. lunata*, *Chaetomium* sp., unidentified

sp. I and IV, *Actinomycetes* sp., and two bacteria. The first four are the causal agents of sheath rot, brown spot, stack burn, and bakanae diseases. Four of the fungi did not sporulate and hence could not be identified. They were sent to the Commonwealth Mycological Institute for identification. Grain spotting, to which BR8 is susceptible, is lowest during boro. Further work on grain spotting and discoloration is in progress. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Tungro propagation

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A method for propagating tungro-infected rice seedlings and tungro vectors was developed. It consists of 1) rearing tungro vectors *Nephotettix virescens* and providing a tungro source for a constant supply of viruliferous insects, 2) raising

TN1 seedlings in a seedbed covered with improvised wooden cages with metal screens, 3) inoculating the seedlings by releasing viruliferous insects into the cages, and 4) transplanting the seedlings after exposure to the viruliferous insects.

A field prepared as a seedbed was divided into eight sections (see photo). Each section is a plot. 1.3 × 3.8 m, subdivided into three lots, each about 1 × 1 m. Two sections of the seedbed are